

Self-Awakening of The Psyche in Girish Karnad's *Yayati*

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J. Priya

*Ph.D Scholar in English, Bharathiyar University
Velavan Nagar, S.Kodikulam, Madurai*

Dr. K. Anuradha

*Assistant Professor in English
Government Arts College, Coimbatore*

Abstract

*Girish Karnad is one of the most prominent Indian dramatists of contemporary Indian Drama. His plays are truly a critique of modern Indian society but his major aim is the exploitation of human relationships and psychology. What is unique about Karnad is his use of history and myth, the juxtaposition of the past and present and various innovations that he has brought into modern Indian Drama. Girish Karnad reworks on the actual myth and adds contemporary attachments with it. Karnad modifies the myth in a way to suit his own plot. And this myth was transformed to reflect the contemporary society. Hermeneutics is the study of the philosophy of understanding and interpreting. Depth or Negative hermeneutics goes below the waking consciousness. Karnad has taken the plot of the play *Yayati* from Adiparva myth of Mahabharata in which *Yayati* was cursed by *Shukracharya* (*Devayani's* father) for his relationship with *Sharmistha* of premature old age. *Sharmistha's* son *Puru* rescues *Yayati* from the curse. *Yayati* is a play on theme of responsibility but *Yayati* himself is not ready to shoulder his responsibility. All the characters resemble the modern race of selfish, immoral and thankless individuals who constitute the majority in contemporary society.*

Keywords: myth, hermeneutics, philosophy, responsibility, psychology, immoral.

Myths are the eternal source of inspiration for creative writers. Myths are expression of the primordial images in the collective unconscious of man. In the beginning, man had certain experiences and received them in his psyche in the form of images. Since they are the images, they are called archetypes of the collective unconscious. Among the modern Indian writers Girish Karnad is one of the leading writers who have made the use of the myth in his creative works. . In his article, "Indian Mythology" Professor R.N. Dandekar says: "If philosophy attempts to discover the ultimate truth, mythology must be said to represent the human effort to attain at least the penultimate truth, of which all experience is the temporal reflection.... Philosophy is often described as the foundation of religion, ritual its super-structure, and mythology as its detailed decoration. In case of Hinduism...mythology is its essential constituent factor.... Mythology represents some of the distinctive features of Hinduism,

tolerance broad sympathy, liberal outlook and dynamic assimilative and at the same time elevating power”

Girish Karnad is one of the most prominent Indian dramatists of contemporary Indian Drama. Like the other playwrights of the 1970's namely Badal Sircar and Vijay Tendulkar, Karnad too was acutely aware of his own glorified tradition. He uses this idea of tradition as his foundation stone and history and myth as his building blocks. His plays are truly a critique of modern Indian society but his major aim is the exploitation of human relationships and psychology. What is unique about Karnad is his use of history, the juxtaposition of the past and present and various innovations that he has brought into Modern Indian Drama.

Girish Karnad has found myths a powerful vehicle to carry the complex ideas of the modern times. Besides the use of myths which enables him to link the continuity of emotions from the beginning of civilization to the present age. Girish Karnad reworks on the actual myth and adds contemporary attachments with it. Karnad modifies the myth in a way to suit his own plot. And this myth was transformed to reflect the contemporary society. Actually Karnad does not interpret the myth as in the past he modifies and questions it. In the view of the theorists of negative hermeneutics writes Prof. Nila Das in her discussion on *The Fire and the Rain* “the purpose of interpretation of an ancient text is not to manifest or restore the text's past meaning in its own terms, but rather to use modern concepts to question demystify and undermine its meaning. It has the idea that an ancient text is a revelation of meaning inherited from posterity. It is a message or proclamation addressed to the audience”(26). Karnad certainly does the line of negative interpretation in his plays right from the beginning. In this paper I have tried to show on the concept of myth and how Karnad have interpreted the myth in a different way.

Hermeneutics is the study of the philosophy of understanding and interpreting. Humans interpret everything around them. There are five different types of hermeneutics. They are: Natural, Normative, Scientific, Philosophical and Depth. These five types of hermeneutics are happening all the time; they never stop. Without these we humans as we are would not exist.

Depth or Negative hermeneutics goes below the waking consciousness. It states that people want to be liberated from all forms of domination and oppression. An example is the fact that people that are not oppressed do not want to be but do not think about it until they are. Negative or depth hermeneutics is the hermeneutics of distrust or suspicion, a continuation of the enlightenment's effort to liberate us from the dogma, error, and superstition of the past. It is called negative because of its undermining intent and is sometimes styled “depth hermeneutics” because it purports to sound beneath linguistic surfaces to the unconscious (Freud) or to the economic political conditions, the regimes of power, that control human communication.

Karnad has taken the plot of the play *Yayati* from Adiparva myth of Mahabharata in which Yayati was cursed by Shukracharya (Devayani's father) for his relationship with Sharmistha of premature old age. Sharmistha's son Puru rescues Yayati from the curse. Yayati is a play on theme of responsibility but Yayati himself is not ready to shoulder his responsibility. At last he accepts it after enjoying youth for one thousand years. In Girish Karnad's *Yayati*, he accepts it after the death of Chitrlekha.

Girish Karnad has given this traditional tale a new meaning and significance highly relevant in the context of life today. The symbolic themes of Yayati's attachment to life and its pleasures as also his final renunciation are retained. In *The Mahabharata*, Yayati recognizes that fulfillment of desire does not diminish or finish it. In Karnad's play, however, Yayati recognizes the horror of his own life and assumes his moral responsibility after a series of symbolic encounters.

In *Yayati* he realized the meaninglessness of sensual pleasures only after the death of Chitrlekha. Chitrlekha's suicide opens the eyes of Yayati, who now readily owns the responsibility and returns

the youth of Puru to him and retires into the forest as a hermit. Karnad here presents two types of characters, on the one hand rejects passionate attachments to sensual pleasures to which the king is a slave, and pleads for a life of responsibilities and self-sacrifice as represented by Puru in the play. Chitralkha's proposal to Yayati turned youth by exchange of ages to accept her may be a test to Yayati's sensuality on the one hand, and on the other it may be Chitralkha's selfishness. His words are expressive of his mind towards the end of the play, "We should wash our sins by doing penance in the forest. I have spent my youth in this city but will spend my old age in the forest" (Yayati 82).

In this play Karnad has interpreted myth in a different way. He questions it and by including new characters like Chitralkha and Swarnalatha he reveals what is there in the subconscious minds of the characters. If Shukracharya does not curse Yayati, his wish for sensual pleasures won't be revealed. And Puru's love for his father will be diminished. Nobody would have noticed his self-sacrifice. If Chitralkha lives, Yayati would not have realized his mistakes as well as his responsibilities. It is Sharmistha who lives with unconditional love for Yayati. She knows that he got married to Devayani and his relationships with other women as being a Kshatriya. Towards the end of the play she goes along with Yayati to the forest to the rest of her life. Devayani being possessive does not have the love and affection for Yayati which Sharmistha has more.

The play offers alternative visions of life. First of Yayati who indulges in the pleasures of the body and the authority to rule; second of Puru who believes that to sacrifice unconditionally is the way to a true living, and third of Chitralkha who wishes to live with self-esteem which requires courage to choose even death.

Here, in the case of Chitralkha, Karnad has given us an insight into a substantial new woman who would not accept oppression and sacrifice herself at any cost. Yayati advises her to retain her calm and self-control, and receive the prince back in the manner which befits an Agna Princess and Bharata Queen for the prestige of the family. Chitralkha refuses to obey her father-in-law when he orders her to follow his command as a king. She prefers to leave the kingdom and embrace death to making such a compromise in life. The king loses patience and she resolutely asks him: "You hold forth my wifely duties. What about your duty to your son? Did think twice before foisting your troubles on a pliant son?" (Yayati 62). She holds Yayati responsible for Pooru's miserable existence and her wretched plight.

Disgusted with the situation where the father and the son carry their will live for a future of their own obsessions without an iota of consideration for her, she embraces death by drinking poison from the vial which Sharmistha had kept there for herself in revulsion against her blighted future. Sharmistha arouses the conscience of the King by reminding him of the result of his actions: "So here is the foundation of your glorious future, You Majesty. A woman dead, another gone mad and third in danger of her life. Good bye, sir" (68).

I thought there were two options- life and death. No it is living and dying we have to choose between. And you have shown me that dying can go on for all eternity. Suddenly I see myself, my animal body frozen in youth, decaying deliquescing, turning rancid. You are lying on your pyre, child, burning for life, while I sink slowly in this quagmire, my body wrinkles and gasping but unable to gasp anything. (68)

After regaining his youth Pooru feels small and hurt at the sight of Chitralkha's dead body and repents: "We brought you here only to die.... We shall never grasp the meaning of all that you taught us" (69). At last Pooru had a moral vision of life with a sense of sacrifice and duty only by losing Chitralkha.

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